

Macroeconomic Developments in Canada: From the COVID-19 Recession to Economic Slowdown (2019–2025)

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<p>Keywords: Canada; Macroeconomics, COVID-19, Economic Recovery, Inflation, Monetary Policy, Fiscal Policy, Bank of Canada, GDP, Interest Rates, Housing Market, Productivity</p> <p>JEL Codes: E31, E52, E62, E65, F43</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Abstract</p> <p>This paper examines the macroeconomic developments in Canada from the COVID-19 recession to the subsequent period of economic slowdown between 2019 and 2025. The study analyzes how the Canadian economy responded to one of the most severe economic shocks in modern history through a combination of expansionary fiscal policy and accommodative monetary policy, followed by an aggressive monetary tightening cycle aimed at restoring price stability. Using data from Statistics Canada, the Bank of Canada, the OECD, FRED, and other official sources, the paper evaluates changes in key macroeconomic indicators, including real GDP, inflation, unemployment, investment, household debt, government expenditure, external trade, and interest rates. The analysis shows that emergency fiscal support and highly accommodative monetary policy played a crucial role in stabilizing economic activity during the pandemic and supporting the post-pandemic recovery. However, these policies also contributed to inflationary pressures that required rapid policy tightening beginning in 2022. The study further demonstrates how higher interest rates weakened household consumption, housing activity, and business investment, while structural challenges such as weak productivity growth, high household indebtedness, and dependence on commodity exports continued to constrain Canada's long-term economic performance. Overall, the paper highlights the policy trade-off between maintaining price stability and sustaining economic growth in a small and open advanced economy.</p>
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Introduction

Canada is one of the world's largest advanced economies and a member of the G7. Despite its relatively small population, the country plays an important role in the global economy through its abundant natural resources, strong financial institutions, highly educated workforce, and close integration with international trade networks. Canada is particularly dependent on exports, with the United States accounting for approximately three-quarters of its merchandise exports. In addition, the energy sector remains a key pillar of economic activity, making the economy highly sensitive to fluctuations in global commodity prices.

Compared with many advanced economies, Canada entered the COVID-19 pandemic with a relatively strong fiscal position and one of the lowest net debt-to-GDP ratios in the G7. However, the economy also faced important structural vulnerabilities, including high household indebtedness,

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weak productivity growth, and a significant dependence on housing activity and commodity exports. These characteristics shaped both the severity of the pandemic shock and the nature of the subsequent recovery. As discussed in the following chapters, these underlying structural conditions influenced the effectiveness of fiscal and monetary policy responses throughout the crisis period. The COVID-19 pandemic produced the sharpest economic contraction in Canada since the Great Depression. Lockdowns, supply chain disruptions, and the collapse in consumer spending caused real GDP to fall dramatically during the second quarter of 2020. As illustrated in Figure 1, Canada's real GDP declined sharply during the pandemic before recovering steadily in the following years. Although output eventually exceeded its pre-pandemic level, the recovery was accompanied by new economic challenges, including rising inflation, labour market imbalances, and growing concerns regarding housing affordability and productivity growth.

Figure 1: GDP, Canada
Source: FRED

Following the initial recovery, strong consumer demand, expansionary fiscal policies, and global supply constraints contributed to a surge in inflation during 2022. In response, the Bank of Canada implemented one of the most aggressive monetary tightening cycles in its history, raising interest rates rapidly to restore price stability. While these measures successfully reduced inflationary pressures, they also slowed household consumption, weakened investment activity, and contributed to a period of lower economic growth between 2023 and 2026.

This study examines the evolution of the Canadian economy from the COVID-19 recession to the post-pandemic recovery and subsequent slowdown period. Using macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, inflation, labour market conditions, fiscal policy, monetary policy, investment, and external trade, the study aims to evaluate how Canada responded to one of the most significant economic shocks in modern history. By analysing these three interconnected phases, the paper seeks to explain both the strengths and structural weaknesses of the Canadian economy and assess the challenges facing policymakers in balancing economic growth with price stability.

The Impact of COVID-19

The pandemic Covid-19 impacted the global economy as one of the biggest contractions after the Great Depression. In early 2020 the biggest wave of Covid-19 hit and effected global trade and supply chains. Trade slowed, schools closed, many businesses were brought to shut down point as the world economy was halted in lockdown.

Canada faced the same restrictions as other countries and there were some consequences leading recession. As other countries, Canada did its part and implemented restrictions and lockdown to restrain the spreading of the virus.

To understand the Canadian economy deeply as it faced Covid 19 in early 2020 let's examine the economy as the time Canada faced covid 19. When COVID-19 reached Canada in early 2020, the economy looked stable on the surface, but there were already important weaknesses underneath. Unemployment was low, consumer spending was steady, and the banking system was stronger than during the 2008 financial crisis. However, Canada was entering the pandemic with slowing growth, weak investment spending, high household debt, and strong dependence on oil and commodity markets.

According to Statistics Canada GDP Data, Canada's real GDP growth in 2019 was approximately 1.6%, showing that the economy was still growing but at a slower pace than previous years. Business investment had also weakened due to global trade uncertainty and lower confidence in the energy sector, especially after the decline in oil prices beginning in 2014. This slowdown in investment spending reduced Canada's economic resilience before the pandemic.

At the same time, household debt had reached nearly 175% of disposable income, meaning Canadians owed far more than they earned annually. Much of this debt came from mortgages, particularly in expensive housing markets like Toronto and Vancouver. The Bank of Canada had already warned that highly indebted households could face serious financial difficulties if incomes suddenly declined. As shown in **Figure 2**, the sustained rise in Canada's household debt-to-income ratio in the years leading up to 2020 illustrates precisely this pre-existing vulnerability — the economy was already stretched before the first lockdown began.

Prices	Contributions to percent change											
Seasonal adjustment	Seasonally adjusted at annual rates											
Geography	Canada (map)											
Estimates	Q1 2019	Q2 2019	Q3 2019	Q4 2019	Q1 2020	Q2 2020	Q3 2020	Q4 2020	Q1 2021	Q2 2021	Q3 2021	Q4 2021
	Percent											
Final consumption expenditure	0.222	0.127	0.442	0.598	-1.227	-9.016	8.356	0.612	0.546	0.218	2.916	0.723
Household final consumption expenditure	0.306	0.136	0.248	0.380	-1.215	-8.098	6.952	0.259	0.270	-0.021	2.795	0.532
Goods	0.098	0.049	-0.004	0.007	-0.813	-2.026	4.065	0.010	0.031	-0.550	0.754	0.053
Durable goods	0.028	-0.027	-0.011	-0.043	-0.836	-0.902	2.295	0.013	-0.114	-0.099	0.069	0.068
Semi-durable goods	0.025	0.042	-0.010	0.017	-0.371	-0.564	1.052	-0.074	0.024	-0.142	0.567	0.006
Non-durable goods	0.045	0.034	0.018	0.033	0.394	-0.559	0.718	0.072	0.121	-0.308	0.118	-0.021
Services	0.208	0.087	0.252	0.373	-0.402	-6.073	2.887	0.248	0.239	0.529	2.040	0.480
Non-profit institutions serving households' final consumption expenditure	0.009	0.006	0.027	0.033	0.012	-0.120	0.069	0.050	-0.046	-0.009	0.020	0.035
General governments final consumption expenditure	-0.093	-0.015	0.167	0.185	-0.025	-0.797	1.335	0.303	0.321	0.247	0.101	0.156
Gross fixed capital formation	0.409	-0.053	0.478	-0.176	-0.363	-2.997	3.356	0.622	0.809	0.368	-0.821	0.368
Business gross fixed capital formation	0.417	-0.052	0.375	-0.169	-0.378	-2.950	3.211	0.619	0.786	0.427	-0.825	0.337
Residential structures	-0.128	0.210	0.144	0.026	-0.320	-0.994	2.429	0.313	0.559	-0.150	-0.831	0.076
Non-residential structures, machinery and equipment	0.474	-0.218	0.230	-0.160	-0.128	-1.812	0.669	0.247	0.049	0.510	0.001	0.286
Non-residential structures	0.097	0.020	0.168	0.080	-0.032	-0.907	-0.091	-0.042	0.239	0.180	0.086	0.139
Machinery and equipment	0.377	-0.238	0.061	-0.240	-0.096	-0.905	0.761	0.289	-0.190	0.330	-0.086	0.148
Intellectual property products	0.072	-0.044	0.001	-0.034	0.070	-0.144	0.112	0.060	0.178	0.066	0.005	-0.025

Non-profit institutions serving households' gross fixed capital formation	-0.008	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.003	-0.002	0.009	0.004	0.002	0.003	-0.004	0.002
General governments gross fixed capital formation	-0.001	-0.002	0.103	-0.009	0.012	-0.045	0.136	-0.001	0.021	-0.062	0.009	0.028
Investment in inventories	0.464	-0.432	-0.442	0.127	0.135	-1.812	-0.223	1.160	0.389	0.236	-0.302	1.313
Of which: business investment in inventories	0.467	-0.427	-0.442	0.116	0.203	-2.025	-0.002	1.097	0.216	0.430	-0.281	1.203
Non-farm	0.426	-0.366	-0.588	-0.005	0.290	-1.926	0.285	0.975	0.428	0.427	-0.286	0.903
Farm	0.041	-0.061	0.146	0.120	-0.086	-0.099	-0.287	0.122	-0.212	0.003	0.005	0.300
Exports of goods and services	-0.017	1.295	-0.284	-0.673	-0.542	-4.885	3.748	0.356	0.816	-1.056	-0.050	0.992
Exports of goods	-0.379	1.081	-0.397	-0.551	-0.097	-4.152	3.664	0.208	0.455	-1.139	-0.269	0.725
Exports of services	0.362	0.214	0.114	-0.123	-0.444	-0.733	0.084	0.148	0.361	0.083	0.219	0.267
Less: imports of goods and services	0.910	-0.173	-0.204	-0.416	0.038	-7.770	6.212	0.892	0.854	-0.102	-0.314	1.576
Imports of goods	0.683	-0.108	-0.217	-0.613	-0.069	-5.440	6.001	0.692	0.417	-0.213	-0.523	1.280
Imports of services	0.227	-0.065	0.013	0.197	0.106	-2.331	0.212	0.200	0.437	0.111	0.209	0.296
Statistical discrepancy	0.074	-0.016	-0.119	-0.006	0.084	-0.060	0.059	0.021	-0.002	0.014	-0.043	-0.030
Gross domestic product at market prices	0.241	1.095	0.280	0.286	-1.950	-11.000	9.084	1.878	1.704	-0.117	2.015	1.790
Final domestic demand	0.630	0.074	0.920	0.422	-1.590	-12.013	11.712	1.234	1.354	0.586	2.095	1.091

Figure 2: GDP by Expenditure, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

Overall, Canada entered the pandemic with relatively strong labour market conditions but also with structural vulnerabilities such as slowing investment spending, high household debt, and dependence on commodity exports. These weaknesses amplified the economic impact of COVID-19.

As Canada faced the first lockdown in in March 2020, economy not just slowed but collapsed with a speed. According to the Statistics of Canada real GDP fell by 7.5% in March 2020 with reduction in public and private goods and services leading reduction on Final domestic demand. Also For the full year 2020, final domestic demand fell approximately 4.5%. As we analyze this economic contraction during 2020 and 2021 we have to know the components of GDP which are, consumption, investment, government spending, net exports.

$$Y=C+I+G+(X-M)$$

Y: GDP

C: Consumption I: Investment

G: Government Spending (X-M): Net Exports

As a result of the lockdowns and restrictions on social interactions, spending on tourism, restaurants, transportation, and entertainment services reduced. There was also an uncertainty about future income and employment conditions so many households postponed non-essential consumption during pandemic. As the consumption is the component of the aggregate demand, huge decline in consumption lead to decreasing aggregate demand. As aggregate demand weakened sharply, many firms faced falling revenues and excess inventories, limiting their ability to increase prices. According to Statistics Canada, Canada’s CPI inflation rate fell to approximately 0.1% in April 2020, reflecting extremely weak consumer demand during lockdown periods. As shown in **Figure 3**, CPI inflation declined sharply during the first lockdown, a clear signal that the economy had entered deflationary territory driven by collapsed demand.

Figure 3: CPI Inflation Rate, Canada
Source: FRED

Gross fixed capital formation and business investment spending declined due to uncertainty, weak revenues, future expectations, supply chain disruptions, and uncertain future market conditions. Many businesses lost confidence and delayed or canceled investment spendings. As shown in **Figure 4**, real business investment per available worker fell noticeably around 2020 across all categories — structures, machinery and equipment, and intellectual property products — continuing a downward trend that had already begun after the 2014 oil price collapse. Notably, the structures component, which had been the dominant driver of investment since the commodity boom, remained severely depressed, signalling that Canada's longer-run investment weakness predated the pandemic and was only deepened by it.

Figure 4: Real Business Investment per Available Worker by Type

Figure 4: Real Business Investment per Available Worker by Type, Canada 1991–2025
Source: CD. Howe Institute

Decreasing investment spending addicted aggregate demand negatively leading a increasing recessionary expectations. However, as monetary policy support expanded through quantitative easing and forward guidance, borrowing conditions gradually improved and investment activity began recovering during late 2020 and 2021.

Figure 5: Energy Export Prices, Canada
Source: FRED

As we lookout the Net exports component of GDP. Canada’s export sector highly depends on oil, natural gas, and commodity exports. As global demand decreased during the pandemic, Energy-producing provinces such as Alberta experienced severe economic pressure as oil prices sharply declined in 2020. As illustrated in **Figure 5**, the sharp drop in global oil and commodity prices amplified Canada's vulnerability, export revenues fell, reducing corporate profits, household incomes, and government tax revenues simultaneously.

Lower foreign demand reduced exports revenues and effected negatively the economic growth. As the domestic demand decreased, imports also decreased and reduced industrial activities. The decline in exports also indirectly worsened Canada’s fiscal position. Lower export revenues reduced corporate profits, household income, and overall tax revenues collected by the government. At the same time, declining economic activity increased government spending through unemployment benefits, income support programs, and fiscal stimulus measures. Consequently, falling exports and imports contributed to a larger federal budget deficit and rising public debt during the pandemic period. **Figure 6** show the movement in Canada's trade volumes, illustrating how the collapse in global demand hit Canada's trade balance from both sides. Because Canada is highly dependent on commodity exports, especially oil and natural gas, the collapse in global energy demand placed significant pressure on both provincial and federal government revenues in 2020.

Figure 6: Trade Volumes (Exports & Imports), Canada
Source: Statistics Canada

As other components decreased, government expenditures increased strongly. The Canadian Government introduced large-scale fiscal stimulus programs to support households and businesses during the recession. Although many households experienced job losses or reduced working hours, direct government transfers such as CERB temporarily increased disposable income for millions of Canadians. Since lockdowns limited opportunities for travel, entertainment, and service consumption, many households accumulated excess savings during 2020. As shown in **Figure 7**,

the household saving rate rose to historically high levels in Q2 2020 — an important consequence of income support arriving at a moment when spending was impossible.

Figure 7: Household Saving Rate, Canada
Source: OECD

Government transfers therefore partially offset the negative effects of rising unemployment on household balance sheets. However, expansionary fiscal policy also caused a significant increase in public debt levels. As shown in **figure 8**, Canada’s federal debt-to-GDP ratio rose sharply as emergency spending programs expanded throughout 2020 and 2021. While these measures stabilized aggregate demand in the short run, they increased long-run fiscal pressures for the government. At the end, the increase in Government Expenditure component slightly stabilized collapse in demand and helped the economy from collapsing. From a Keynesian perspective, expansionary fiscal policy was necessary to support aggregate demand and reduce the depth of the recession.

Figure 8: Net Debt-to-GDP Ratio, Canada**Source:** FRED

Canada faced the economic crisis that Covid 19 caused with a strong balance sheet the lowest net debt-to-GDP ratio in the G7, and historically low borrowing rates. The Canada Government take a strong planned action to stimulate the economy. The first priority was to protect the health and safety of Canadians than support households, workers, and businesses.

The Canadian government implemented large-scale expansionary fiscal policies to offset the collapse in private sector demand and reduce the depth of the recession. Between mid-March and the end of November 2020, the federal government committed over \$212 billion in direct support to Canadians and businesses — combined with \$85 billion in tax and customs duty deferrals and approximately \$600 billion in liquidity support, bringing the total potential intervention to well over \$400 billion in federal measures alone. Total COVID-related federal spending between March and November 2020 represented approximately 64% of all federal spending recorded in the entire fiscal year 2019, and was projected to raise Canada's national debt to \$1.06 trillion — an increase of \$343 billion from pre-pandemic levels. As shown in **Figure 9**, when federal and provincial measures are combined, total government support reached \$469 billion — with direct spending alone accounting for \$256 billion, 91% of which was delivered by the federal government. These supports represent a clear example of a Keynesian demand-management approach.

Canada's COVID-19 Economic Response –Federal, Provincial and Territorial Support Summary

	Federal	Provincial and Territorial	Total
Impact (\$ billions)¹			
Direct²	231.9	24.1	256.0
Tax, Customs Duty payment and Fee Deferrals	85.0	38.2	123.2
Liquidity³	86.5	3.3	89.8
Total	403.4	65.6	469.0
Share of Spending (per cent)			
Direct	91	9	100
Tax, Customs Duty payment and Fee Deferrals	69	31	100
Liquidity	96	4	100
Total	86	14	100

Figure 9: Canada's COVID-19 Economic Response**Source:** Statistics Canada

One of the largest fiscal support programs was the Canada Emergency Response Benefit (CERB), introduced on March 25, 2020. This program was aiming to provide taxable benefit of \$2,000 every four weeks — up to a maximum of \$14,000 over 28 weeks to workers who lost their jobs due to the pandemic. By the end of the program, according to the Government of Canada, approximately 8.9 million Canadians received CERB support. The total cost was approximately \$81.6 billion and this makes the single largest direct spending measure in the federal response. As shown in **Figure 10**, CERB transfers directly supported household disposable income at a moment when wage income was collapsing as it is stabilising consumption spending despite rising

unemployment. This policy helped sustain household consumption spending despite rising unemployment levels.

Geography	Canada ¹ (map)				
Estimates	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Dollars				
Household disposable income	1,224,918	1,280,362	1,387,661	1,431,275	1,502,340
Plus: social transfers in kind ²	336,961	349,855	369,730	401,574	430,602
Equals: adjusted household disposable income	1,561,879	1,630,217	1,757,391	1,832,849	1,932,942
Adjusted household disposable income	1,561,879	1,630,217	1,757,391	1,832,849	1,932,942
Minus: household actual final consumption	1,597,407	1,650,671	1,595,726	1,737,931	1,941,984
Plus: change in pension entitlements	43,259	47,476	38,999	42,432	40,585
Equals: household net saving	7,731	27,022	200,664	137,350	31,543

Figure 10: Household Disposable Income & Transfer Payments, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

Another policy was the Canada Emergency Wage Subsidy (CEWS) which was designed to prevent mass layoffs by subsidizing employee wages for firms experiencing revenue losses. CEWS provided up to 75% of eligible employee remuneration, to a maximum of \$847 per week, to employers facing revenue declines due to COVID-19 disruptions. By reducing labour cost, CEWS gave opportunity to employers to re-hire their workers when they are ready to be back at work as soon as public health measures allow. According to the 2021 budget, expenses of CEWS were \$84.6 billion for fiscal year 2020/2021. This makes CERB, one of the two largest individual spending measures in Canadian fiscal history. Businesses that used CEWS between March and September 2020 had a closure rate 10.9 percentage points lower than businesses that did not. As illustrated in **Figure 10**, the stabilisation of household disposable income during this period — supported jointly by CERB transfers and CEWS-backed wage retention — also moderated the sharp spike in household savings observed in 2020, as employment continuity gradually restored consumer confidence and spending capacity. Where CERB supported individuals who had lost work, the Canada Emergency Wage Subsidy (CEWS) was designed to keep the employee-employer relationship intact by subsidising payroll costs directly.

Beyond CERB, CEWS, and CESB, the government deployed \$5.5 billion in financial support for low- and modest-income Canadians, measures to protect seniors facing volatile retirement savings, the Business Credit Availability Program (BCAP), and the Canada Emergency Commercial Rent Assistance (CECRA). The government aimed to reduce the stress among firms, support business continuity, and prevent bankruptcies during lockdown periods. As a result of these expansionary fiscal policies, As private consumption and business investment collapsed in Q2 2020, government expenditure surged — rising 23.8% annually. Without these policies GDP could have contracted by more than 10% in 2020 and unemployment could have risen even further. However, the cost was the federal deficit reaching \$343.2 billion in FY 2020/2021, compared with \$34.4 billion in the pre-pandemic fiscal year. Although these policies stabilized the short run economic activity and prevented a deeper depression. As seen in the **Figure 8**, the government significantly increased Canada's debt-to-GDP ratio. Expansionary fiscal policy shifted aggregate demand (AD) outward during a period of severe demand-side contraction.

The Canadian labour market experienced Lockdown measures, mobility restrictions, and temporary business closures caused a rapid deterioration in employment conditions throughout 2020. According to the Statistics Canada Labour Force Survey, Canada’s unemployment rate increased sharply and reached approximately 13.5% in May 2020. This represented one of the highest unemployment levels observed in recent decades from a pre-pandemic low of approximately 5.6% in February. As shown in **Figure 11**, the speed of the unemployment spike was historically unprecedented, with millions of jobs lost within a matter of weeks rather than

Unemployment rate at record high

Source(s): Table 14-10-0287-01 (formerly CANSIM table 282-0087).

months.

Figure 11: Unemployment Rate, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

Employment losses were particularly concentrated in service-based industries requiring face-to-face interaction, such as tourism, hospitality, retail trade, and transportation. Government intervention partially stabilized labour market conditions through wage subsidies and income support programs. CERB and CEWS reduced the long-term effects of unemployment by supporting household income and helping firms retain workers during periods of weak economic activity.

Labour market shock directly effected the consumption channel. Households income was primarily derived from salaries and wages. Rise of unemployment and reduced working hours tighten consumer spending capacity and reduced aggregate demand when businesses most needed revenue. Labour force participation also declined during the pandemic because economic uncertainty discouraged job search activity. As firms reduced production and investment, labour demand weakened significantly across the economy. Rising unemployment contributed to a negative output gap in the Canadian economy and intensified recessionary pressures during 2020.

The scale of government intervention was decisive in limiting this damage. As shown in **Figure 12**, without direct support measures, real GDP would have contracted by approximately 10% and unemployment would have reached around 12% — compared to the actual outcomes of roughly –6% GDP growth and ~10% unemployment. This comparison illustrates that fiscal policy did not merely soften the recession at the margins; it prevented a significantly deeper economic collapse.

Figure 12: Impact of Direct Support Measures on Real GDP Growth and Unemployment Rate, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

During Covid 19 lockdowns reduced consumption, investment, and business activity, aggregate demand declined sharply. In response the Bank of Canada implemented strong expansionary monetary policy measures to support the economy and stabilize financial markets. Monetary policy aimed to lower borrowing costs, increase liquidity, and maintain the flow of credit to households and firms. Bank of Canada followed three distinct policy: emergency interest rate cuts, large-scale asset purchases (quantitative easing), and a suite of liquidity and market-functioning programs covering nearly every major credit market segment.

As shown in **Figure 13**, The Bank of Canada entered the pandemic with a policy rate of 1.75% and in March 2020, the Bank of Canada cut its policy interest rate from 1.75% to 0.25%, which was considered the effective lower bound. The rate remained at this historic low until March 2022, when tightening began in response to post-pandemic inflation. The aim was to reduce the cost of borrowing for consumers and businesses, supporting spending, investment, and debt repayment capacity at a moment when private income and revenue were collapsing. Lower short term rates also affected the housing market. Five-year fixed mortgage rates fell to levels not seen in decades and this led to the housing investment surge of 30.7% recorded in Q3 2020.

Figure 13: Interest Rates, Canada

Source: FRED

The sudden closure of some part of the Canadian economy early 2020 created severe shock waves in financial markets. Since the economy was uncertain for a while as the consequence of the pandemic, businesses and investors rushed to sell assets and raise cash. As a response to this case, the Bank of Canada introduced quantitative easing (QE) and large-scale asset purchase programs in early 2020, in addition to interest rate cuts. These programs involved purchasing government bonds and other financial assets to inject liquidity into financial markets. This created severe shock waves in financial markets. The goal was to keep credit flowing, restore market functioning, and allow interest rate cuts to pass through the broader economy. When the Bank of Canada buys bonds, this raises the price of the bonds and lowers their yield. Lower yields make it cheaper to access credit, encouraging households and businesses to borrow to spend and invest. QE can also make banks more likely to offer loans by leaving them with more liquidity, enabling them to lend to a wider set of borrowers. By December 2020, the Bank had purchased slightly more than \$180 billion in Government of Canada bonds since the programme launched in March and continued into 2021. By the end of the reinvestment phase, the Government Bond Purchase Program had purchased approximately \$340 billion of government bonds.

Alongside QE, the Bank deployed extraordinary forward guidance — a communication tool designed to influence expectations about future monetary policy. The Bank of Canada announced that interest rate would remain at 0.25% until inflation sustainably returned to the 2% target. Their aim was to reduce uncertainty regarding future borrowing costs. This policy affected the behaviour of households, businesses, and financial markets through the expectations channel of monetary policy transmission. When economic agents believed that interest rates would remain low for an extended period, they became more willing to borrow, invest, and spend. For businesses, stable expectations about future low interest rates encouraged long-term investment decisions and credit issuance. For households, forward guidance supported consumption spending by lowering uncertainty and reducing expected future loan costs. While QE increased liquidity in financial markets, forward guidance influenced expectations and confidence, helping reduce long-term interest rates and supporting recovery in aggregate demand.

The Bank also introduced liquidity facilities and purchase programs to keep credit available for Canadian companies and households. These policies helped stabilize short-term funding markets and ensured that businesses and financial institutions could continue accessing credit during the crisis.

Overall, Canada’s monetary policy response played a critical role in supporting short-run economic recovery. From an AD-AS perspective, the pandemic initially shifted aggregate demand to the left because households reduced the consumption, firms delayed investment, and uncertainty increased. Fiscal stimulus supported household income and government spending, while monetary policy supported credit conditions. Together, these policies helped reduce the depth of the recession. However, the combination of low interest rates, fiscal expansion, and QE also increased concerns about future inflationary pressures, asset price increases, and the long-term consequences of an expanded central bank balance sheet.

Post-Pandemic Recovery Phase

The Canadian economy experienced a strong economic contraction during the COVID-19 pandemic then, entered a strong recovery phase in 2022. The Government implemented fiscal and monetary policies to support the economic recovery and deployed over \$350 billion in emergency spending. By 2021 with the development and widespread distribution of COVID-19 vaccines and public health restrictions were removed, economic activity gradually recovered, leading to a strong rebound in the Canadian economy with real GDP expanding 5.3%. Canada’s real GDP per capita was USD 200 (0.4%) lower in 2022 than in 2019. Canada’s post-pandemic recovery in real GDP per capita over 2019-22 was the fifth weakest out of 38 OECD countries as shown in **Figure 14**. However, with the recovery, new challenges have emerged as supply-demand imbalances emerged and created an increasing consumer-price inflation. Policymakers implemented various fiscal and monetary measures to address Canada's socio-economic challenges and alleviate the rising cost-of-living pressures faced by households.

Figure 14: Total change in real GDP per capita (%), 2019 to 2022, selected OECD countries
Source: OECD

Prices	Contributions to percent change											
Seasonal adjustment	Seasonally adjusted at annual rates											
Geography	Canada (map)											
Estimates	Q1 2021	Q2 2021	Q3 2021	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023
	Percent											
Final consumption expenditure	0.546	0.218	2.916	0.723	0.630	1.416	0.581	0.465	0.270	0.247	0.376	0.327
Household final consumption expenditure	0.270	-0.021	2.795	0.532	0.402	1.377	0.369	0.275	0.264	0.003	0.108	0.379
Goods	0.031	-0.550	0.754	0.053	0.285	0.131	-0.116	0.011	0.243	-0.061	-0.132	0.273
Durable goods	-0.114	-0.099	0.069	0.068	0.163	-0.092	-0.068	0.029	0.214	-0.066	0.069	0.238
Semi-durable goods	0.024	-0.142	0.567	0.006	-0.034	0.197	-0.055	0.000	0.111	-0.024	-0.140	0.023
Non-durable goods	0.121	-0.308	0.118	-0.021	0.156	0.026	0.008	-0.017	-0.081	0.029	-0.061	0.012
Services	0.239	0.529	2.040	0.480	0.117	1.246	0.485	0.264	0.021	0.064	0.240	0.106
Non-profit institutions serving households' final consumption expenditure	-0.046	-0.009	0.020	0.035	0.024	0.031	0.007	0.004	0.031	0.031	0.018	0.013
General governments final consumption expenditure	0.321	0.247	0.101	0.156	0.204	0.009	0.205	0.185	-0.025	0.213	0.250	-0.065
Gross fixed capital formation	0.809	0.368	-0.821	0.368	0.699	-0.533	-0.382	-0.226	0.084	0.457	-0.148	-0.346
Business gross fixed capital formation	0.786	0.427	-0.825	0.337	0.650	-0.512	-0.281	-0.271	-0.092	0.413	-0.200	-0.394
Residential structures	0.559	-0.150	-0.831	0.076	0.432	-0.844	-0.414	-0.201	-0.326	0.049	0.130	-0.084
Non-residential structures, machinery and equipment	0.049	0.510	0.001	0.286	0.083	0.248	0.105	-0.117	0.202	0.393	-0.337	-0.302
Non-residential structures	0.239	0.180	0.086	0.139	0.092	0.135	0.091	0.150	0.094	0.197	-0.165	-0.240
Machinery and equipment	-0.190	0.330	-0.086	0.148	-0.008	0.114	0.014	-0.267	0.108	0.197	-0.173	-0.062
Intellectual property products	0.178	0.066	0.005	-0.025	0.135	0.084	0.029	0.047	0.032	-0.029	0.007	-0.008

Non-profit institutions serving households' gross fixed capital formation	0.002	0.003	-0.004	0.002	0.007	0.006	-0.002	-0.004	0.010	0.007	0.006	0.007
General governments gross fixed capital formation	0.021	-0.062	0.009	0.028	0.041	-0.027	-0.099	0.049	0.166	0.037	0.045	0.041
Investment in inventories	0.389	0.236	-0.302	1.313	-0.194	1.081	0.204	-1.141	-0.576	-0.076	-0.109	-0.117
Of which: business investment in inventories	0.216	0.430	-0.281	1.203	-0.163	1.060	0.222	-1.048	-0.694	-0.035	0.007	-0.181
Non-farm	0.428	0.427	-0.286	0.903	-0.454	0.850	0.314	-0.784	-0.457	-0.217	0.024	-0.114
Farm	-0.212	0.003	0.005	0.300	0.291	0.210	-0.092	-0.265	-0.237	0.182	-0.017	-0.067
Exports of goods and services	0.816	-1.056	-0.050	0.992	-0.055	1.204	0.386	-0.015	1.181	0.410	-0.053	0.431
Exports of goods	0.455	-1.139	-0.269	0.725	-0.015	0.962	0.089	-0.171	0.814	0.211	-0.167	0.203
Exports of services	0.361	0.083	0.219	0.267	-0.039	0.242	0.297	0.156	0.367	0.199	0.114	0.228
Less: imports of goods and services	0.854	-0.102	-0.314	1.576	0.084	2.003	-0.030	-0.944	-0.088	0.850	0.020	0.224
Imports of goods	0.417	-0.213	-0.523	1.280	0.085	1.459	-0.152	-0.893	-0.262	0.564	-0.173	-0.099
Imports of services	0.437	0.111	0.209	0.296	-0.002	0.545	0.122	-0.051	0.174	0.286	0.192	0.323
Statistical discrepancy	-0.002	0.014	-0.043	-0.030	0.040	-0.028	-0.011	0.036	0.005	-0.029	0.004	-0.019
Gross domestic product at market prices	1.704	-0.117	2.015	1.790	1.037	1.138	0.809	0.063	1.053	0.160	0.050	0.052
Final domestic demand	1.354	0.586	2.095	1.091	1.329	0.883	0.199	0.239	0.354	0.704	0.228	-0.019

Figure 15: GDP by Expenditure, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

In the **Figure 16**, Canada's real GDP grew by **4.2%** in 2022 and this makes the fastest recovery among Canada's last four recessions and the second-strongest recovery in the G7. The growth was based on business investment and household consumption. As shown in **Figure 15**, Household final consumption expenditure increased strongly as labour income was recovered and consumer confidence improved. One of the main drivers of recovery was the reopening of contact-intensive industries such as tourism, hospitality, transportation, entertainment, and retail services. During lockdown periods, households accumulated excess savings because opportunities for travel, recreation, and service consumption were limited. As restrictions eased, pent-up consumer demand contributed to a sharp increase in spending activity. In addition, high global energy prices following Russia's invasion of Ukraine boosted revenues in Canada's energy sector, supporting overall economic growth. However, economic growth began to slow in the second half of 2022. To control rising inflation, the Bank of Canada increased interest rates several times. Higher borrowing costs reduced demand for mortgages and consumer loans, leading to weaker housing market activity and lower household spending.

Figure 16: GDP Growth (annual %), Canada
Source: OECD

As seen in the **Figure 15**, Government final consumption expenditure contributed positively throughout 2021 with operation of pandemic-era fiscal support programs. The scale of fiscal support in this period — over \$350 billion in federal emergency spending since 2020 — meant that household incomes were largely protected through the pandemic, and government itself became a significant demand driver. This is precisely what Keynesian stabilization policy is designed to do: replace private demand that has collapsed with public demand, preventing a deeper and longer recession.

In the second quarter of 2022, household consumption increased aggressively. At the same time business were able to restock and rebuild inventories after the supply chain was recovering from the pandemic. The combination of surging consumer demand and inventory rebuilding increased GDP. However, inflation surged mostly because of the increasing household demand. As seen in the **Figure 17**, Canada’s CPI inflation rate rose to approximately 6.8% in 2022, significantly above the Bank of Canada’s 2% inflation target. Energy prices, food prices, housing costs, and transportation expenses increased rapidly during this period. The housing market also contributed to inflationary pressures. Extremely low interest rates during 2020–2021 stimulated mortgage borrowing and housing demand, leading to rapid increases in housing prices and rent costs.

Figure 17: CPI, Canada
Source: FRED

The data in the residential structures in the **Figure 15**, shows how quickly the housing boom ended. Canadians with variable-rate mortgages began seeing their payments rise, new buyers faced higher qualifying rates, and home sales dropped sharply. This outcome illustrates why housing is the fastest monetary policy transmission channel: unlike business investment or consumer spending, which adapted slowly, the housing market responds to interest rate changes almost immediately through mortgage pricing.

The Canadian labour market recovered rapidly and unemployment rate declined to approximately 5% during 2022 as seen in the **Table 28**. The recovery was supported by reopening service sectors, rising labour demand, and continued economic expansion. Strong labour demand increased wage pressures and contributed further to increasing inflation. However, because CPI inflation was running at 6–8% through most of 2022, real wages (inflation-adjusted) were falling and workers were earning more in dollar terms but losing purchasing power.

Table 18: Annual Labour Statistics, Canada
Source: FRED

Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022 caused global oil prices to rise sharply, with oil prices exceeding \$120 per barrel. As a major energy exporter, Canada benefited from higher energy exports and increased revenues in the oil sector. Higher corporate profits generated additional tax revenues for the government, which helped reduce the federal budget deficit faster than expected. However, imports also increased significantly during this period. Many Canadians spent the savings accumulated during the pandemic on imported goods and international travel. As a result, the rise in imports offset much of the increase in exports, limiting the overall contribution of net exports to GDP growth.

The Government's contribution was steady and positive throughout 2021 and 2022. Fiscal policy did not cause the 2022 inflation spike directly and household consumption was the dominant driver. However, the cumulative effect of \$314 billion in pandemic-era transfers had built a reserve of household purchasing power that was released all at once in Q2 2022. The government consumption contributions remaining consistently positive in 2023. This illustrates that government demand was not meaningfully tightening even as the Bank of Canada was raising rates aggressively making a real instance of policy mix tension.

Figure 19: Central Government Debt, (total % GDP) for Canada
Source: Fred

During Pandemic, Emergency programs; including CERB, CEWS, and CERS drove the federal deficit to an estimated \$314 billion in 2020–2021, pushing the federal debt-to-GDP ratio from approximately 31% to 45% in two years. As seen in **Figure 19**, Debt-to-GDP ratio fell from 45.4% to 42.2% in 2022–2023 for two main reasons: the federal deficit shrank sharply as pandemic support programs (CERB, CEWS, etc.) expired and stopped draining the budget, and elevated commodity prices following the Russia-Ukraine war generated unexpected windfall tax revenues. At the same time, the denominator (nominal GDP) grew rapidly, partly because high inflation itself inflates the dollar value of output.

The Bank of Canada had reduced its overnight policy rate to 0.25% in March 2020 and launched quantitative easing (QE) to keep credit flowing. By March 2022 as inflation was already climbing sharply, the Bank raised its policy rate to 5.00% as seen in the **Figure 20**. Besides rate hikes, the Bank of Canada launched Quantitative Tightening (QT) in April 2022, allowing government bonds purchased during the QE phase to mature without reinvestment. Unlike the pandemic period, when Quantitative Easing increased the money supply and injected liquidity into the economy, QT reduced the amount of money circulating in financial markets. As liquidity declined, long-term interest rates increased, making borrowing more expensive for households and businesses. Higher borrowing costs slowed consumption and investment spending, reducing aggregate demand and helping to ease inflationary pressures.

Figure 20: Interest Rates, Canada

Source: FRED

The housing market responded first to QT, as higher interest rates increased mortgage costs and reduced demand for new homes. At the same time, higher mortgage interest payments increased housing-related costs for households and contributed to inflation measurements. Canadian households faced growing financial pressure as borrowing became more expensive. Also, as seen in the **Figure 21**, Canadian households entered the tightening cycle with a high level of indebtedness, making them particularly sensitive to higher interest rates. Mortgage and other debt interest payments rose significantly, reducing disposable income available for consumption. As a result, consumer spending slowed and households became more cautious, leading to a higher saving rate in contrast, the labour market remained relatively strong despite tighter financial conditions. Employment levels stayed high and unemployment remained low, suggesting that labour market adjustments occurred more slowly than changes in housing activity and consumer spending. This persistence indicated that monetary policy would need time to fully reduce demand and bring inflation back to target levels.

Figure 21: Household Debt to GDP, Canada

Source: FRED

Canada's economic growth gradually weakened throughout 2022 and 2023 as the effects of monetary tightening spread across the economy. The Bank of Canada's rapid interest rate increases, combined with Quantitative Tightening (QT), successfully reduced aggregate demand by raising borrowing costs for households and businesses.

The first effects appeared in the housing market, where residential investment declined sharply as higher mortgage rates reduced housing affordability and new construction activity. Household consumption also lost momentum, particularly in discretionary services such as travel, recreation, and restaurants, as rising debt servicing costs reduced disposable income. At the same time, business fixed investment remained weak throughout 2022 and 2023, reflecting both higher financing costs and Canada's longer-term productivity challenges.

As a result, the main domestic components of GDP—consumption and investment—contributed less to economic growth than they had during the post-pandemic recovery period. Quarterly GDP growth slowed significantly compared with the strong rebound observed in 2021 and early 2022.

However, economic activity did not contract sharply. Several factors helped cushion the impact of tighter monetary policy. Government investment remained supportive, exports benefited from strong commodity prices and recovering global services trade, and rapid population growth

sustained overall consumer demand despite weaker per capita spending. In addition, labour market conditions remained relatively strong, preventing a collapse in household income and confidence.

Overall, the slowdown in 2022–2023 reflected the intended effects of monetary policy rather than a broader economic crisis. Inflationary pressures gradually eased as demand moderated, while positive contributions from exports, public spending, and population growth helped Canada avoid a deep recession. This outcome suggests that the Bank of Canada largely achieved a "soft landing": economic growth slowed substantially, but the economy remained resilient enough to prevent a severe contraction.

Economic Slowdown Phase

Following the rapid post-pandemic recovery and inflation surge of 2022, the Canadian economy entered a period of significantly slower growth between 2023 and 2026. Unlike the pandemic recession of 2020, this slowdown was not caused by lockdowns or a collapse in economic activity. Instead, it emerged as a consequence of deliberate policy actions taken to restore price stability.

The economy was effectively overheating, forcing policymakers to shift their focus from economic stimulus toward price stabilization. By mid-2022, inflation had reached levels not seen in decades, forcing the Bank of Canada to implement one of the most aggressive monetary tightening cycles in its history. Between March 2022 and July 2023, the policy interest rate increased from 0.25% to 5.00%. Higher borrowing costs, gradually reduced household spending; weakened housing activity; and discouraged business investment. As a result, aggregate demand began to slow throughout 2023 and remained subdued during the following years. The expenditure data reveal that the slowdown was not driven by a single GDP component. Rather, it reflected a combination of weaker household consumption, declining investment activity, volatile external trade performance, and the gradual withdrawal of pandemic-era fiscal support. The economy was effectively overheating, forcing policymakers to shift their focus from economic stimulus toward price stabilization.

Prices	Contributions to percent change												
Seasonal adjustment	Seasonally adjusted at annual rates												
Geography	Canada (map)												
Estimates	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024	Q4 2024	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026
	Percent												
Final consumption expenditure	0.270	0.247	0.376	0.327	0.587	0.445	0.895	0.486	0.259	0.807	-0.221	0.514	0.141
Household final consumption expenditure	0.264	0.003	0.108	0.379	0.263	0.204	0.619	0.352	0.159	0.582	-0.111	0.387	0.198
Goods	0.243	-0.061	-0.132	0.273	-0.076	0.050	0.271	0.321	0.077	0.117	-0.094	-0.010	0.042
Durable goods	0.214	-0.066	0.069	0.238	-0.042	-0.082	0.143	0.146	-0.082	0.024	-0.075	-0.042	-0.109
Semi-durable goods	0.111	-0.024	-0.140	0.023	0.025	0.053	0.035	0.096	0.087	0.016	0.019	0.010	-0.017
Non-durable goods	-0.081	0.029	-0.061	0.012	-0.059	0.080	0.094	0.079	0.071	0.077	-0.038	0.023	0.169
Services	0.021	0.064	0.240	0.106	0.340	0.154	0.348	0.031	0.082	0.465	-0.017	0.396	0.156
Non-profit institutions serving households' final consumption expenditure	0.031	0.031	0.018	0.013	0.001	0.002	0.007	0.008	0.001	0.006	0.008	0.002	-0.003
General governments final consumption expenditure	-0.025	0.213	0.250	-0.065	0.323	0.239	0.269	0.126	0.099	0.219	-0.118	0.125	-0.054
Gross fixed capital formation	0.084	0.457	-0.148	-0.346	0.079	0.300	-0.135	0.557	-0.216	0.085	0.091	0.157	-0.250
Business gross fixed capital formation	-0.092	0.413	-0.200	-0.394	-0.025	0.246	-0.161	0.479	-0.203	-0.025	-0.064	-0.079	-0.136
Residential structures	-0.326	0.049	0.130	-0.084	-0.105	-0.084	0.138	0.265	-0.204	0.004	0.082	-0.181	-0.146
Non-residential structures, machinery and equipment	0.202	0.393	-0.337	-0.302	0.047	0.309	-0.325	0.211	0.005	-0.009	-0.133	0.048	-0.070
Non-residential structures	0.094	0.197	-0.165	-0.240	0.030	0.125	-0.029	0.042	-0.044	0.134	-0.013	-0.016	-0.146
Machinery and equipment	0.108	0.197	-0.173	-0.062	0.017	0.184	-0.296	0.170	0.049	-0.143	-0.120	0.064	0.076
Intellectual property products	0.032	-0.029	0.007	-0.008	0.033	0.021	0.026	0.003	-0.004	-0.020	-0.012	0.054	0.080

Non-profit institutions serving households' gross fixed capital formation	0.010	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.006	0.003	0.004	0.001	-0.007	0.011	0.006	0.001	-0.005
General governments gross fixed capital formation	0.166	0.037	0.045	0.041	0.098	0.051	0.022	0.076	-0.006	0.099	0.149	0.235	-0.110
Investment in inventories	-0.576	-0.076	-0.109	-0.117	0.063	0.299	-0.098	-0.987	0.530	1.044	-0.587	-1.216	1.068
Of which: business investment in inventories	-0.694	-0.035	0.007	-0.181	0.094	0.224	-0.097	-0.989	0.550	1.050	-0.596	-1.191	1.048
Non-farm	-0.457	-0.217	0.024	-0.114	-0.017	0.221	-0.059	-0.910	0.305	0.859	-0.666	-0.884	0.997
Farm	-0.237	0.182	-0.017	-0.067	0.111	0.003	-0.038	-0.079	0.245	0.191	0.069	-0.307	0.050
Exports of goods and services	1.181	0.410	-0.053	0.431	-0.181	-0.084	-0.052	0.719	0.362	-2.115	0.305	0.497	-0.042
Exports of goods	0.814	0.211	-0.167	0.203	-0.156	-0.014	-0.036	0.604	0.435	-2.082	0.277	0.533	-0.058
Exports of services	0.367	0.199	0.114	0.228	-0.025	-0.070	-0.015	0.116	-0.073	-0.033	0.029	-0.037	0.016
Less: imports of goods and services	-0.088	0.850	0.020	0.224	-0.189	0.167	-0.195	0.035	0.292	0.101	-0.926	0.155	0.910
Imports of goods	-0.262	0.564	-0.173	-0.099	-0.116	0.365	-0.291	0.178	0.398	-0.196	-0.735	0.029	0.914
Imports of services	0.174	0.286	0.192	0.323	-0.073	-0.197	0.096	-0.143	-0.106	0.297	-0.190	0.127	-0.004
Statistical discrepancy	0.005	-0.029	0.004	-0.019	-0.009	0.023	0.013	-0.038	0.072	0.038	-0.041	-0.043	-0.043
Gross domestic product at market prices	1.053	0.160	0.050	0.052	0.729	0.816	0.819	0.701	0.716	-0.242	0.472	-0.246	-0.036
Final domestic demand	0.354	0.704	0.228	-0.019	0.667	0.745	0.760	1.043	0.044	0.891	-0.131	0.671	-0.109

Figure 22: GDP by Expenditure, Canada

Source: Statistics Canada

To restore price stability, the Bank of Canada implemented one of the most aggressive tightening cycles in its history. Between March 2022 and July 2023, the policy interest rate increased from 0.25% to 5.00%, as seen in **Figure 23** the primary objective of this tightening was to reduce aggregate demand by increasing borrowing costs throughout the economy. One of the most important transmission mechanisms was the mortgage renewal shock. During the pandemic, many Canadian households obtained mortgages at historically low rates of around 1–2%. However, as illustrated in **Figure 24**, conventional mortgage lending rates rose rapidly throughout 2022, increasing from 3.44% in January 2022 to 5.89% in December 2022. As these low-rate mortgages came up for renewal between 2024 and 2026, many borrowers faced significantly higher financing costs, often exceeding 5%. Consequently, monthly mortgage payments increased by several hundred dollars for many households, reducing disposable income available for consumption. According to Statistics Canada, household debt-service ratios also increased during this period as interest expenses rose. This helps explain why household consumption became a weaker contributor to GDP growth during the slowdown phase, reflecting the effectiveness of monetary tightening in moderating aggregate demand.

Figure 23: Interest Rates, Canada

Source: Fred

Geography	January 2022	February 2022	March 2022	April 2022	May 2022	June 2022	July 2022	August 2022	September 2022	October 2022	November 2022	December 2022	January 2023
	Percent												
Canada (map)	3.44	3.58	3.77	4.19	4.63	5.05	5.51	5.58	5.64	5.75	5.88	5.89	5.86

Figure 24: Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation, conventional mortgage lending rate

Source: Statistics Canada

The investment sector experienced an even stronger response to monetary tightening. Higher interest rates increased the cost of capital, making new investment projects less attractive for businesses. **Figure 22** highlights that business gross fixed capital formation contributed positively to GDP growth during early 2025, reaching 0.479 percentage points in Q1 2025. However, as financing conditions tightened further and economic uncertainty increased, business investment weakened substantially and reached -0.136 percentage points by Q1 2026. The slowdown in housing activity also coincided with a growing housing affordability crisis. Higher mortgage rates increased borrowing costs at a time when housing prices remained elevated. As a result, many households were priced out of the housing market, reducing home purchases and residential investment. This affordability challenge became one of the most important structural issues facing the Canadian economy during the slowdown period.

The decline in investment also had broader implications for future economic growth. Both the OECD and the Business Council of Canada have repeatedly highlighted that Canada has experienced persistently weak productivity growth compared with other advanced economies. As illustrated in **Figure 25**, Canada's forecast labour productivity growth for 2024 remained close to zero and significantly below that of several OECD peers. Continued weakness in capital investment therefore represents not only a short-run growth problem but also a long-run challenge to Canada's economic potential.

Figure 9.3. Country-level labour productivity growth, nowcast for 2024

Predicted labour productivity growth per country, Per cent

Figure 25: Country-level labour productivity growth, nowcast for 2024

Source: OECD

As illustrated in **Figure 26**, lower household spending reduced firms' revenues in the goods and services market. In response, firms scaled back investment and hiring, weakening labour demand in factor markets. This contributed to a rise in Canada's unemployment rate from 5.0% in early 2023 to 5.8% by the end of the year. Wage growth also moderated from the elevated rates seen during the post-pandemic recovery, limiting household income level and purchasing power. As a result, weaker wages further constrained consumer spending, causing a broader economic slowdown.

Figure 26: Circular Flow Diagram

Although total GDP continued to grow slightly, population growth was even faster. In 2023, Canada's real GDP grew by approximately 1.1%, while the population increased by a record 3.2%, rising from about 39.5 million to 40.8 million people. As a result, GDP per capita declined, meaning that economic output per person was falling despite positive aggregate growth. This led many economists to describe the period as a "per-capita recession," because living standards were weakening even though the economy continued to expand overall.

Canada's economic performance remained highly dependent on external demand throughout the slowdown period. Approximately three-quarters of Canadian exports are directed to the United States, making the economy particularly vulnerable to fluctuations in U.S. growth and global commodity markets. As shown in **Figure 22** exports contributed 1.181 percentage points to GDP growth in Q1 2023 and 0.719 percentage points in Q4 2024. However, export performance deteriorated sharply in Q2 2025, when exports contributed -2.115 percentage points to GDP growth.

A major source of this volatility was the energy sector. Canada is one of the world's largest exporters of crude oil and natural gas, meaning that export revenues are closely tied to global energy prices. As illustrated in **Figure 27**, the U.S. landed cost of Canadian crude oil experienced significant fluctuations during recent years. Following the exceptionally high oil prices observed in 2022, energy prices moderated, reducing export revenues and weakening economic activity in export-oriented sectors. Consequently, lower commodity prices and weaker external demand reduced corporate profits, export earnings, and government tax revenues.

At the same time, fiscal policy also shifted substantially. During the pandemic, emergency support measures injected hundreds of billions of dollars into the economy, supporting household income and aggregate demand. By 2023, however, most emergency support programs had expired and the federal government shifted toward fiscal consolidation and deficit reduction. The federal budget deficit declined significantly as emergency spending was withdrawn.

While the government continued issuing bonds to finance remaining deficits and refinance existing debt, higher interest rates increased debt-servicing costs. Combined with slower export growth and weaker commodity-related revenues, this limited fiscal flexibility. As a result, fiscal policy became less expansionary than during the pandemic period, reinforcing the broader slowdown in aggregate demand and GDP growth during the stabilization phase.

U.S. Landed Costs of Canada Crude Oil

 Data source: U.S. Energy Information Administration

Figure 27: U.S. Landed Costs of Canada
Source: U.S Energy Information Administration

The slowdown period highlights one of the most important challenges facing policymakers: balancing inflation control against economic growth.

The Bank of Canada's tightening cycle successfully reduced inflationary pressures. Higher interest rates slowed borrowing, reduced household spending, cooled housing markets, and weakened investment activity. As aggregate demand moderated, inflation gradually moved closer to the Bank's 2% target.

However, these benefits came at a cost. Slower consumption, weaker investment, softer labour market conditions, and lower GDP growth were all direct consequences of tighter monetary policy.

This trade-off is central to modern macroeconomic policy. Reducing inflation often requires reducing aggregate demand, but weaker demand inevitably slows economic growth. The Canadian experience between 2023 and 2026 demonstrates that price stability and economic growth cannot always be maximized simultaneously.

Ultimately, Canada's slowdown phase represents a transition from post-pandemic expansion toward a more sustainable economic path. While growth weakened compared with the recovery years, inflation stabilization improved the long-run foundations of economic stability and reduced the risk of persistent inflation becoming embedded in the economy.

Conclusion

The Canadian economy experienced a remarkable transition from the severe COVID-19 recession of 2020 to a strong recovery in 2021–2022 and a subsequent slowdown between 2023 and 2026. Expansionary fiscal and monetary policies successfully stabilized economic activity, supported households and businesses, and helped restore growth after the pandemic. However, the rapid recovery also contributed to inflationary pressures, forcing the Bank of Canada to implement aggressive monetary tightening. While higher interest rates helped reduce inflation and restore price stability, they also weakened household consumption, investment, housing activity, and overall economic growth. Furthermore, structural challenges such as high household debt, weak productivity growth, housing affordability issues, and dependence on commodity exports continued to limit Canada's long-term economic performance. Overall, the Canadian case demonstrates the difficult balance policymakers must maintain between supporting economic growth and controlling inflation while ensuring long-term economic sustainability.

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